

METHODS, WAYS & TIPS TO EMPOWER ONESELF & OTHERS FOR BETER MENTAL HEALTH & ADJUSTMENT

Ms. Daksha H. Halkare

Assistant Professor,

Adarsh College of Arts & Commerce, Badlapur

Abstract:

Mental Health affect us all. How we think and feel about ourselves and our lives impact on our behaviour and how we cope under stressful situations. It affects our ability to make the most of the opportunities that come in our life and play an important role in our family, workplace, friends, community, whether we call it well being, emotional welfare or mental health it is key to living a fulfilling life. Mental health is a level of psychological well being or an absence of mental disorder. It is the psychological state of someone who is functioning at a satisfactory level of emotional and behavioural adjustment.

This is the age fact of stress competition & challenges we all are running with the time 24 Hrs & after experiencing corona pandemic & Lockdown situation, new challenges in every field are arising. To deal with all this, we need strong body & strong mind. This paper deals with explaining the meaning, importance of mental health & some ways, methods & tips to enhance and maintain mental health, for better personal. Social & professional adjustment Adoptions & practice of these methods will empower every one of us for in achieving better mental health as well as Physical health, to avoid mental illness.

Key Words – *Mental Health, Physical Health, Mental Illness, Empowerment*

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Objectives:

1. To provide definition & meaning of mental health
2. To explain importance of mental health
3. To suggest ways methods & tips to empower oneself & others for better mental health.

Introduction:

After the very tough time of Covid -19 , to tackle with many situation in we need healthy body as well as healthy mind. To enhance & to maintain our mental health, this paper aims to give tips to be implemented in our life, thoughts habits & attitude. Since concept of health consists mental & social health. We need to make efforts for healthy mind too. 21st century is the age of stress, cut threat competition, breaking relationships increasing depressions & suicides underline the need of strong mind, healthy mental, physical & social approaches in our lines. Mental health is a level of psychological well being or an absence of mental disorder. It is the psychological state of someone who is functioning at a satisfactory level of emotional and behavioural adjustment

Discussion :

Mental health is a state of well being in which the individual realizes his / her own abilities, can cope with normal stresses of life, can work productively & fruitfully & able to make contribution to community Mental health is a positive state of mind & body, feeling safe and able to cope, verity a sense of connection with people, communities & under environment

Mental health includes our emotional psychological & social well being. It affects our action, feeling & thinking & how we handle stressful situation, how we develop & maintain our relations. In short it defines our adjustment to everything in life. If also affects our physical health & if an individual is unable to sustain his mental health for long, he may suffer from psychological disorders, when we are mentally, healthy, we can enjoy our life, we can be creative, we are able to cope with our personal & Professional life in better way , we can prevent psychological illness & therefore we need to apply certain methods & ways to improve & sustain our mental health, so that we can function with full capacity in this competitive world.

Mental health include our total well being that is emotional, social physical and this is significant in our life as it affects directly our adjustment capacity, our stress management and our life as a whole. People who are not having good mental health are disturbed emotionally, show various symptoms such as feeling depressed, helpless, low energy, inability to adjust, having unexplained pains and feelings, aggression or dumbness etc., Mental health and physical health are interrelated. If a person is feeling depressed, he/she is less likely to engage in physical activities that promote good health, in turn, if a person's mobility is restricted due to illness or disease he/she can be prone to feeling of

hopelessness, or despair thus inhibiting their participation in recovery.

In today's context mental health is based on three criterias.

- 1) Individual Criteria : Mentally healthy individual has self-confidence, sense of responsibility tolerance, capacity to cope up with stress in their life situation.
- 2) Social Criteria: behaving in a socially acceptable manner, accepting social norms, having satisfactory interpersonal relations with many people indicate healthy mental state of a person.
- 3) Functional Criteria : How a person functions during stressful situations? Whether he follows mature and positive ways to deal with the problems or not decides about his mental health as per these criterias..

Ways /Methods/Tips For Mental Health.

- 1) Do exercise – physical exercise have positive effect on our body & mind. It can reduce anxiety & depression.
- 2) Eat right – Selecting proper nutritional food is very important because it is must for healthy body & mind.
- 3) **Stress Management is required for better mental health through –**
 - a) Recognize the sources of stress.
 - b) Learning & practicing relaxation technique.
 - c) Enjoying hobbies, activities, rest & relaxation time.
 - d) Sharing your problems with your dear ones, talking about it to feel relax & to get support is very necessary.
 - e) Keep in touch with your friends and relatives.
 - f) Ask for help if required,
 - g) Take a break from work, change of few minutes in activity can reduce your Stress.
 - h) Accepting yourself will help in reducing stress.
 - i) Always try to care for others.
 - j) Develop positive attitude
 - k) Get proper rest and sleep
 - l) Perform small acts of kindness & help others.
 - m) Avoid alcohol, smoking and consumption of drugs
 - n) Cognitive techniques-- review your attitudes and values, restructure your thinking set goals , use positive imagery, rehearse mentally.
 - o) Behavioural changes to better manage interpersonal situation and distress -check

your assumptions, share your expectation with others, be assertive, exercise and consume sensibly.

- p) Techniques to solve conflict of motives such as compromise, attacking the situation (solving conflicts directly) withdrawal, right choice of alternatives and sometimes appropriate use of defense mechanisms.
- q) Meditation has been proven effective in reducing stress. It can help the mind and body achieve a deep state of relaxation. It can also be combined with visual technique to help calm the mind.
- r) Relationship review, review past hurts, forgive, communicate, listen and reward. All these ways and methods can help us to maintain & enhance our mental health by dealing effectively with the stress.

Apart from this, we may use following ways to control and manage our emotions

1. Understanding and accepting our emotions
2. Express your love to your close ones.
3. Take time to laugh and relax.
4. Forgive other.
5. Reward yourself for your good deeds and actions.
6. Value yourself.
7. Try to quiet your mind with relaxation or mindfulness techniques.
8. Break the monotony, go for picnic or small vacation.
9. Yoga or deep breathing exercises are good activities for improving our mental health
10. Maintain your work life balance.
11. We must keep watch on symptoms of failing mental health which are feeling sad continuously, exercise fear/worries, low energy withdrawal from social activities and if needed we must take advice and help by the experts in time to prevent more damage.

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